

Editorial

Truth, Reality, and the Role of Education

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The role of the human educator or teacher is linked to the conception of life as something still in the process of development, not yet fully and completely realized – that is, a life that still offers possibilities or opportunities that may or may not come to realization or fruition, a life that is still free. Conversely, the idea of a world in which no human teacher or educator would be needed, where everything would be merely a matter of unfolding or progress, gradually coming to completion according to already clear rules, would be the vision of a world ruled by a power to which everyone and everything is subjected without freedom. Both the absurdity and the ignorance present themselves in a world that remains productive, yet where freedom is nothing more than an empty phrase, hammered in vain at the gates of such closed worlds, where it becomes a lie, a false slogan, a falsehood.

It is a striking testament to the power of life that, in various concentration camps – where people, forced to live side by side, were supposed to experience a lack of privacy – historical accounts show that there was often a natural, instinctive effort to learn from one another. Not, then, a life side by side, but a life in relation to one another, in which one serves as a teacher or mentor to the other, and under different circumstances their roles may be reversed; that is, a life where the role itself is not so important, but rather the way in which one turns toward or relates to another person, the way in which we live with another human being. In such environments, the need to learn was not an effort to accumulate information, nor a simple exchange of knowledge, but the result of a naturally manifesting need to realize human life, despite the inhuman environment in which they had to live. The emergence of the teacher–student role is, even in such an environment, a sign of humanity, of the experience of human life. Similar experiences included the creation of plays and performances that may not have had any audience, but where people acted and thus expressed their freedom in at least some way. Human culture is thus an expression of the freedom that is inherent to human life.

Education is an expression of the coexistence of the hidden and the manifest, the possible and the actual, the passive and the active, in a world that is still pulsating life. Conversely, the idea of something already wholly and completely realized and actual is an idea of something that is unchanged and constant in every respect. We have no human experience with this, for we ourselves are the ones who are temporal and historically situated, yet at the same time we can form such an idea – namely, the idea of a world beyond all movement, a metaphysical world.

Plato, a witness to such creativity, sought also a way out of such non-living representations (in his case, a way to the highly living Idea, that is not “some idea”, but source of all truth, good, and beauty). Therefore, “Plato would not be Plato if he were not also more than Plato”, as Jan Patočka noted in *Negative Platonism* (Patočka 1953 in Kohák 1989, 182, cf. Patočka 1996, 310 / Patočka 2007, 22).

Philosophers, as lovers of truth, bear witness to the fact that we do not possess the truth, but rather the truth possesses us; that the truth will always transcend us; that it is not enough to uncover the truth, but that even after every experience of the truth, we must always seek it anew. For truth does not lie in experience, that we may have, experiencing through the senses with which we receive what bears upon us, through this passive experience (*passio*). Truth reveals itself only in the experience that we are, which is a different kind of experience in which we do not possess, do not relate to the world of objects or things, and in which we ourselves are not an object either. Truth reveals only in an experience of freedom, which is an experience of distance. Truth is not a description of reality; such a description can only be truthfulness (i.e., veracity or trueness). The role of teaching and education is to distinguish between what has already come to pass, manifested itself and what reveals itself as possibilities that are good and suitable for realization. In this conception, the role of teaching and education remains lifelong or even transcendent, for it always points beyond the existing forms of life to possibilities that transcend what is already given. Thus, the interconnectedness of not only the hidden and the manifest, the possible and the actual, the passive and the active, but also the given and the transcendent, becomes evident.

A person incapable of a student-teacher relationship resembles the charioteer who has lost the white horse from Plato’s image of the soul, in which spirit (enthusiasm) was symbolized by that white horse (Phaedr. 253d; cf. Rep. 440e–441b where described as desirous / Gr. *epithymetikos* / appetite, enthusiastic / Gr. *thymoeides* / spirited, and rational / Gr. *logistikos* / reason). Without enthusiasm or spirit, a person is incapable of shame and is also incapable of experiencing human community, in which the pursuit of what is right, true, and just must be realized (in which that charioteer, i.e., *logos*, also participates). If we were to imagine a person who is merely desiring and rational, then learning would be merely a matter of methods and rules. Such a person would lack the ability to relate to beauty in a moral (not aesthetic) sense – and, also lack the ability to avoid what is morally ugly. Such a person would lack the capacity to experience that we are not behaving as we should (commonly referred to as shame). Of course, the question of “how we should behave” is determined not only by nature but also by culture, habits, and the depth of one’s education and upbringing; therefore, there have always been various ideas about what one should be ashamed of and what one should not (cf. Rep. 441a; Gorg. 484c, 494c–d, 522d; cf. Stránský 2023, 54–58).

In any society, there have probably always been people who have not yet come to realize their own inadequacies, their own limitations, and their own boundaries. “The absence of shame as an inhibitor of behavior leads to the fact that such a person is ready to do anything.” (Daneš 2023, 18) We can only hope that no society will ever lack people capable of serving as good educators or teachers to them, just as Socrates was to Alcibiades – the very person toward

whom Alcibiades first felt a sense of shame (Symp. 216b). The role of education thus remains the same even in the age of so-called artificial intelligence: to awaken us from shadows and illusions to the truth, which we can experience only in the experience that we are, not in the experience that we have, for truth can never be possessed; that is possible only with ideologies, false truths, and illusions. For now, people who do not feel shame often do not even realize what they are actually missing. Yet there is still hope that this will happen for humanity, and that the white horse will lead them as well. However, if we were ever to face a situation where artificial intelligence displays shame, we would encounter a false image, an illusion, a falsehood, a lie masquerading as truth. Uncovering these differences will always be at the very core of life-enriching human bonds or relationships; in the relationship between educator (or teacher) and student, it is certainly essential.

If we imagine a world in which educators and teachers would no longer be needed, we are imagining a metaphysical concept that does not yet correspond to our experience – neither to the experience we are, nor to the experience we have. Philosophers and theologians of education have always pointed out this difference, and although they often used words to create images depicting such metaphysical ideas, nevertheless, if they perceived that philosophy is philosophy only when it is education, and that theology is theology only when it is education, then these were images of the goal toward which they were striving, though a goal they only hinted at, one that lies beyond the limits of our corporeality, beyond the limits of the corporeal, physical world. But to try to pretend even now to live in such a world should be prevented by human shame, through which truth protects us from succumbing to the illusion that everything is already accomplished and that free choice is unnecessary.

Theology and Philosophy of Education opens the first issue of the fifth volume with the article *The Pathos of Knowing: Affectivity, Gnosticism, and Education* by Robert Farrugia, where phenomenology of knowing is examined in the context of education. Pope Francis's critique of the contemporary Gnosticism and call for a renewed inquiry into the foundations of knowledge that begins with the lived experience is here, among other things, presented.

Jeff Frank offers concept of education as a poetics of value creation through the lenses of Luke Burgis's call for serious philosophical anthropology, where life at the intersections of the three cities, Athens, Jerusalem and Silicon Valley, could be grounded. Science, technology, and society as partners for a dialogue where a new model of authority can grow is the focus of analyses in the article *Conceptualising Authority in a Technologized World* by Michal Černý. Bert Meeuwsen presents conceptual and reflective framework for cultivating ethical judgement in the current conditions of epistemological plurality. Describing his 'Pluriversal Ethical Reflection Framework', he claims that „[p]lurality can enrich educational experience“.

Narcissism as a mechanism of moral blindness is defined in the following article by Tibor Máhrík. He examines how individualism takes shape in a situation where the fundamental need is to be seen, recognized, and admired, and where moral decision-making has shifted from the realm of cognition and knowledge to that of immediate impulses and emotional experience.

Value formation provided through imagination and myth is examined in Robert Falzon's article which explores a non-coercive framework for ethical and existential formation. He argues that myth allows the freedom of imagination without leading to ethical irrelevance.

Critical observation, ethical evaluation, responsible action and examining Aristotle's four causes are steps on the path to transformation presented in Roland Urbain's continuing contribution from the previous issue of our journal. The aim is to show how practical intelligence can be activated.

Dear readers, I hope that your charioteer will guide you safely through all the journeys that lie ahead, and that all your encounters will be opportunities for the joyful experience of freedom, understanding, and transcendence that you are,
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